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Didimera tourism village development strategy in Timor Leste

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Abstract

A tourism village is a rural area that has developed its natural, cultural or historical tourism potential to attract tourists. This research aims to understand community perceptions regarding the development of Didimera Tourism, Vessoru village, Uatolari sub-district, Viqueque District, Timor Leste, designing beach-based religious tourism designs, inventorying tourist facilities, involving stakeholders, and formulating tourism village development strategies. The data collection techniques used in this research are: documentation, observation, in-depth interviews, and Focus Group Discussion (FGD). Data analysis was carried out using the SWOT analysis method, which includes identifying strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats in the development of the Didimera Tourism Village. The research results show that the development of the Didimera Religious Tourism Village in Vessoru Village, Uatolari District, Viqueque District has great potential to improve the local economy, preserve culture and the environment, and provide a memorable tourism experience for visitors. Didimera tourism village development strategy based on local communities that is holistic and sustainable.

Keywords: Tourism Village; Development Strategy; Timor Leste; Beach-Based Religious Tourism; SWOT Analysis

1. Introduction

A tourism village is a rural area that has developed its natural, cultural or historical tourism potential to attract tourists. Individuals or groups of people visit certain places for various purposes according to their needs, such as recreation, personal development, or learning about the uniqueness of the tourist attractions visited for a short time (Sutono, et al., 2023; Nurohman & Qurniawati, 2021). The tourism village concept aims to generate income for local communities, as well as preserving culture and the environment in accordance with the principles of sustainable development (Atmoko, 2021). The development of the Didimera tourist village in Vessoru Village, Uatolari subdistrict, Viqueque District can build intensive communication between the community and tourists.

In developing tourist villages around Didimera, the concept (Community Based Tourism CBT) will be used to involve the community because the community is one of the important sectors that plays a role in tourism development and is able to manage and develop tourist attractions on their own. Tourism activities bring social, economic and cultural influences that arise as an effect of tourist travel (Pradana, 2019). Sudibya's research (2018) concluded that local communities act as hosts and are important actors in the development of tourist villages in all stages starting from the planning, monitoring and implementation stages. As part of tourism activities, in tourist villages there are various collections of businesses that provide goods and services to facilitate business activities, have fun and utilize free time away from the environment where they live (Utama, 2014).

Didimera Tourism, which is located in Vessoru village, Uatolari subdistrict, Viqueque district, Timor Leste, is a tourist spot that has natural riches that are able to attract local tourists and other districts to visit the place, so it needs to be

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developed in order to increase the number of visitors. The number of visitors on Christmas and New Year reaches 2000 (Ministerio do Turismo, 2013), but the facilities are still relatively few and do not seem to be able to meet the welfare of the surrounding community, therefore, in order for the Didimera tourist attraction to be better developed, it is necessary to carry out a SWOT analysis to find out and understand the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (Nisak, 2004; Putri, et al., 2022) at the Didimera tourist attraction, Vessoru village, Uatolari sub-district, Viqueque district, Timor Leste.

Various studies have been carried out on the development of tourist villages in Indonesia. Tourist villages in general have several strengths and weaknesses but have not been utilized optimally (Ramadhan, 2023). The potential of tourist villages in general is also very diverse (Martitah et al., 2022). The large amount of potential that can be developed means that village tourist attractions can emerge as superior regional products (Nurlina, et al., 2021). Destiana, et al. (2022) found several potentials that could be developed in the Baros Tourism Village, Bandung Regency, including the development of tourist village institutions, development of tourist objects and attractions and development of tourist infrastructure. Firsty & Suryasih (2019) found that tourism development still faces several strategic issues that need to be addressed, such as the need to optimize efforts for each stakeholder in carrying out their duties, such as zoning which must be determined as quickly as possible, policy making and promotional efforts which must be optimized.

Looking at the phenomena and problems that occur, the research questions that can be formulated in this research are: (a) What is the perception of the people of Vessoru Village, Uatolari District, Viqueque District regarding the development of the Didimera Religious Tourism Village?; (b) What is the design of beach-based religious tourism in Didimera, Vessoru village, Uatolari District, Viqueque District?; (c); How to inventory tourist facilities to support the development of the Didimera tourist destination, Vessoru village, Uatolari sub-district, Viqueque district?; (d) How are stakeholders involved in developing Didimera tourism in Vessoru village?; (e) What is the strategy for developing a local community-based tourism village in the area around Didimera, Vessoru village, Uatolari sub-district, Viqueque district?

Referring to the problem above, the objectives of this research are: (a) to determine the perceptions of the people of Vessoru Village, Uatolari District, Viqueque District regarding the development of the Didimera Religious Tourism Village; (b) Create a beach-based religious tourism design in Didimera, Vessoru village, Uatolari District, Viqueque District; (c) Taking inventory of tourist facilities to support the development of the Didimera tourist destination, Vessoru village, Uatolari sub-district, Viqueque district; (d) Involving Vessoru village stakeholders for the development of Didimera tourism; (e) Formulate a strategy for developing a beach-based tourist village in the area around Didimera, Vessoru village, Uatolari sub-district, Viqueque district.

2. Methods

The research method used in this research is an exploratory descriptive method with a qualitative approach. The data sources in this research were 12 people, namely the people who sell products in that place and the structure of Vessoru village. Data collection techniques in research are interviews, observation, documentation and focus group discussions.

The qualitative data analysis technique in this research uses SWOT analysis. In the SWOT analysis, the internal and external environment is identified. Didimera Tourism Village has an environment consisting of internal and external environments that can be developed into developing tourism. Internal environmental factors consist of strengths and weaknesses, while the external environment is related to opportunities and threats. The data collection techniques for this research are documentation/library study, observation and exploration of the research area, in-depth interviews and focus group discussions (FGD).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Overview of Research Setting

The research was conducted at Didimera Tourism, which is located at the foot of Mount Didimera with beautiful beaches and cool air. Didimera nature tourism is one of the tourist attractions located in the Vessoru village area, Uatolari District, Viqueque District, Timor Leste. Vessoru Village borders the eastern part of Uatocarbau District which is a lowland area, from the western part Babulo village is lowland and to the north Babulo village is highland. The entire area of Vessoru Village is 32.93 km², Vessoru village has 6 villages, namely Balabasiba, Mau-Boru, Uani-Uma, Baha-Buga, Culu-Dere, Baha-o and Matau. The total population of Vessoru village is 1,701 people. Based on its government structure, the Vessoru Village government consists of the Village Head, using a maximum pattern consisting of the Village Head,

Village Secretary, village traditional leader, village youth leader, 7 RKs per village, with a total of 11 people (Republica Democratica de Timor Leste., 2002).

To find out the development strategy in the Didimera tourist area, Vessoru village, researchers collected data by interviewing people who sell their products in the Didimera tourist area, visitors and tourism stakeholders. Apart from that, researchers also documented the conditions of Didimera tourism, visitors, sellers, photos of Focus Group Discussion (FGD) activities, activities in the Didimera tourist area, the structure of Vessoru village and stakeholders in the tourist area. Next, make observations on the condition of the Didimera tourist area, the activities of the community selling their products, selling their work, visitors, the Vessoru village government and the Vessoru youth association.

3.2. Community Perceptions of the Development of the Didimera Religious Tourism Village

Community perception is the way individuals in a community understand and interpret the world around them based on existing experiences, values, beliefs and cultural influences. This includes how they see and respond to information, events and situations that occur in their daily lives (Kemalasari & Sugiri, 2023). With the development of religious tourism in the area around Didimera, Vessoru village, it can be said to be suitable for implementation because the local community expressed positive attitudes towards this because with the development of Didimera tourism they can promote the values of their beliefs such as religion, tradition and culture, promote their work so that very supportive in development.

Research data obtained from the perceptions of the people of Vessoru Village, Uatolari District, Viqueque District regarding the development of the existing Didimera Religious Tourism Village were distributed to 37 respondents. The respondents in this study were all parties who were part of the research sample, namely from the seven RKs in Vessoru village, the youth leader of Vessoru village, ten land owners near the Didimera tourist area, ten people from food and drink sellers in Didimera and eight people from the youth of Vessoru village.

Based on the results of a descriptive analysis of the Vessoru Village community's perception of the development of the Didimera Religious Tourism Village, it can be concluded that the majority of respondents (60%) belonged to the SS group, who stated that they strongly agreed with the development strategy. Meanwhile, a small portion of respondents (27%) belonged to group S, who stated they agreed with this strategy. Meanwhile, the TS and STS groups, who stated they did not agree and strongly disagree, only comprised 8% and 5% of the total respondents respectively, indicating that their percentages were very small. From these results, it can be concluded that the majority of the people of Vessoru Village tend to support the development of the Didimera Religious Tourism Village, although there are also a small number who disagree or strongly disagree.

To build a perception that better supports the development of the Didimera tourist village, these are:

- Education and Information

Providing clear and comprehensive information to the public regarding the benefits that will be obtained from the development of Didimera religious tourism because of the potential for economic improvement, preserving culture and traditions, as well as improving infrastructure and public services. In this way, people who have not approved the land around Didimera tourism will understand the benefits of developing this tourism.

- Community Involvement

Involving the community in the decision-making and tourism development planning process through active participation, the community can feel ownership in the development of Didimera tourism and be more accepting of proposed changes.

- Transparency and Openness

Ensure that all information related to the development of Didimera religious tourism is conveyed honestly and transparently to the public

- Local Economic Empowerment

Increase engagement and economic benefits for local communities, such as through skills training, employment opportunities, and development of small and medium enterprises.

- Cultural and Environmental Preservation

Ensure that tourism development is carried out by paying attention to cultural and environmental sustainability. This includes maintaining the authenticity of religious sites, preserving cultural heritage, and minimizing negative impacts on the environment.

By taking these steps, the people of Vessoru Village will have a more positive perception of the development of the Didimera Religious Tourism Village, and their support for the Didimera tourism development process will be stronger.

3.3. Beach Based Religious Tourism Design

Religious tourism refers to temporary and short trips of people to destinations outside their place of residence and daily activities to visit religious sites. Religious tourism destinations have meaning that can be used as a guide to convey religious teachings throughout the world (Romadoni et al., 2023).

Didimera Cave is a unique destination, which combines the natural charm of the beach with a strong spiritual aura. Located between towering cliffs and waves crashing on the shore, Didimera Cave has long been considered a holy place by various Catholic religious communities. By utilizing the natural riches and religious values contained therein, the development of religious tourism in Didimera Cave has great potential to become a center of spirituality and reflection for visitors.

The results of the Focus Group Discussion regarding the design of religious tourism in Didimera all focused on the Didimera natural cave which had a statue of Jesus Christ built to promote it because the cave is one of the unique things that attracts tourists. The design of religious tourism in Didimera highlights the focus on the development of Didimera Cave which has been built with the statue of Jesus Christ as the center of attention. Research and discussions in the FGD confirmed that Didimera Cave is unique and very attractive to tourists, and therefore, its development needs to be prioritized. From a research perspective, it can be concluded that the emphasis on Didimera Cave as the main attraction is the result of the analysis of tourist preferences and interests carried out. Data from the research shows that the statue of Jesus Christ and the cave environment provide a significant spiritual and aesthetic experience for visitors, which makes it a focal point in planning the development of religious tourism destinations in Didimera. The results of the FGD also showed that the participants agreed that the development of Didimera Cave was the right step to increase the attractiveness of religious tourism in the area. The discussion involved ideas for improving infrastructure, supporting services and tourist experiences around the Didimera Cave location. Further steps include planning for facility development, destination promotion, and other efforts aimed at maximizing the potential of tourists who are interested in the spiritual and cultural aspects of the tourist destination.

The design of beach-based religious tourism in Didimera Cave and its environment includes various elements and is part of the Didimera tourist area development strategy to create a unique and memorable experience for visitors (Erlangga & Endartuti, 2022; Mulyani, 2021).

Here are some steps regarding the design:

- Combining the Natural Charm of the Beach and the Spiritual Aura will combine the natural beauty of the beach, such as clear sea water, and stunning views with a strong spiritual aura from sacred places such as areas for meditation or reflection located around caves near towering cliffs.
- Supporting facilities such as places of worship, meditation rooms and rest areas. These facilities will ensure that visitors' comfort and practical needs are met during their visit.
- consider the environmental impacts of developing religious tourism on the coast. The design must pay attention to the principles of sustainability and environmental conservation so as not to damage the natural ecosystem around the cave.
- Promotion and Marketing. The success of the design around the Didimera cave environment will also be greatly influenced by effective promotion and marketing efforts and communicating the uniqueness and spiritual appeal of the Didimera religious tourism destination to all visitors can increase their interest and visits.

This design is considered appropriate because it combines beautiful natural elements with the spiritual power of Didimera Cave to maintain the natural and religious uniqueness of the place. This design can attract tourists who are interested in spiritual experiences and natural beauty. Factors that influence the success of beach-based Didimera religious tourism design are the quality of destination management and marketing, support from the government and local communities, environmental maintenance, and the quality of the facilities and services provided. By taking all

these factors into account, the design has the potential to become a successful and sustainable religious tourism destination.

3.4. Didimera Tourism Facilities

Vessoru Village, located in an area rich in natural beauty and cultural heritage, offers a unique tourist experience for its visitors. One of the main attractions in this village is Didimera, a stunning tourist destination with a combination of stunning beaches and natural beauty at the foot of a majestic mountain. As part of efforts to promote local tourism and provide unforgettable experiences for visitors, it is important to understand and identify the tourist facilities available in the Didimera tourist area. An inventory of these facilities is an important step in understanding existing tourism infrastructure and evaluating the need for further development.

In this research, the author will explore the inventory of Didimera tourist facilities in Vessoru Village. The discussion will cover the various facilities available around the beach and the three caves which are the main attractions in this area. By understanding existing facilities, you can explore opportunities to improve the tourist experience and support sustainable tourism development in Vessoru Village.

Tourism facilities that need to be inventoried and have become a necessity for tourists in the Didimera tourist area are as follows:

- Accommodation

In an effort to better welcome visitors and boost the local tourism industry, it is important to ensure the availability of adequate accommodation around Didimera. Quality accommodation not only provides a comfortable resting place for visitors, but can also be a determining factor in attracting tourists to spend more time in the area. The results of researchers' observations at the Didimera Tourist Destination show that there is no accommodation or lodging for tourists. However, based on the existing potential, researchers see that around Didimera, a simple accommodation can be built for tourists, but it is not sufficient as accommodation.

- Places to Eat and Drink

As part of the tourist experience, eating and drinking facilities in Didimera are important to support visitor comfort and satisfaction. The results of the researchers' observations have not found a provider of places to eat and drink that are very good for tourists. The existing facilities are simple restaurants and are inadequate. Restaurants and eateries in tourist destinations have a unique appeal that reflects the rich culture, culinary traditions and local heritage of the area. In the Didimera tourist area, researchers found eating and drinking houses that exude unique culture and attractive flavors and several characteristics that are often found in eating and drinking houses in that place, such as ketupat, saboko, hakmerik, aifarina desak, and grilled fish. With the presence of dishes such as ketupat, saboko, hakmerik, aifarina desak, and grilled fish, restaurants and drinks in the Didimera tourist area offer an unforgettable culinary experience for visitors. The authentic taste and diversity of these dishes are an integral part of Didimera's charm and tourist attraction. Even though Didimera's specialties can be the main attraction, the restaurant facilities and environment there still have several shortcomings and must be improved in order to provide comfort for tourists.

- Public facilities

Didimera, as an attractive tourist destination, has great potential to attract visitors from various places. However, to ensure a satisfying tourism experience for every visitor, it is important to provide adequate public facilities. Existing public facilities include public toilets, rubbish bins, natural caves / Gruta Didimera which are places of worship, parking areas, seating areas, rest and recreation areas. These facilities not only meet visitors' basic needs, but also create a comfortable, safe and friendly environment. In this study, researchers conducted direct observations and found that public facilities were still lacking and inadequate. Existing facilities such as toilets, rubbish bins, caves/gruta, parking lots, seating areas, rest and recreation areas have not been well managed, whereas these facilities are really needed by tourists and also cleanliness in the Didimera tourist area is still lacking and this can be seen from the condition of the toilets. In general, it is not yet suitable as a facility in tourist areas. This is because management by local communities in the Didimera tourist area is voluntary and there is no special manager for Didimera tourism.

The development of tourism destinations is greatly influenced by several facilities, including supporting facilities such as transportation, education and health (Erlangga & Endartuti, 2022).

The village of Vessoru, with its stunning natural beauty and extraordinary underwater biodiversity and natural caves has become an attractive destination for tourists looking for a different and authentic experience in the Didimera region. In an effort to develop the tourism potential of Vessoru Village, it is important to pay attention to the role of tourist facilities in supporting the growth and sustainability of the Didimera tourist destination. In the context of developing appropriate and sustainable tourist facilities is the key to increasing attractiveness and comfort for visiting tourists, existing facilities are currently inadequate because public tourist facilities not only enrich the tourist experience, but also have the potential to have a positive impact on the economy. local as well as environmental and cultural preservation. Through this discussion, researchers will explore various types of tourist facilities that can be developed in Vessoru Village to support the holistic and sustainable development of the Didimera tourist destination. From tourist information centers to local arts and crafts centers, every facility has an important role to play in enriching the tourist experience and promoting tourism sustainability.

With facilities that support the Didimera tourist destination, Vessoru village are:

- Homestays and Accommodation.

Having a homestay or other accommodation that is comfortable and affordable can increase the tourist attraction of Vessoru Village and tourists who stay longer will have the opportunity to learn more about local culture and lifestyle.

- Tourist Information Center

Complete tourist information center to help tourists in planning their visit. Information about tourist attractions, available activities, as well as local maps and guides can be provided

- Local Dining and Culinary Places

Restaurants or food stalls that offer local and traditional cuisine will be an attraction for tourists who want to try regional specialties. Serving delicious and varied food can also enhance their tourism experience.

- Handicraft Center: A handicraft center that sells local handicraft products can be an attractive place for tourists to shop for souvenirs. It can also support the local economy by empowering local craftspeople.
- Recreational Facilities: Recreational facilities such as playgrounds, picnic areas, or sports facilities such as beach volleyball courts or soccer fields can add to the variety of activities that tourists, especially those who come with families, can enjoy.
- Health and Fitness Center: To attract tourists interested in health and fitness, facilities such as a fitness center, spa, or yoga center could be offered in Vessoru Village.
- Waste Management and Public Toilets: It is important to provide good waste management facilities and clean and well-maintained public toilets for the comfort and cleanliness of the environment.

By providing various quality and varied tourist facilities, Vessoru Village can increase its appeal as an attractive and sustainable Didimera tourist destination. It is also important to pay attention to sustainability in the development of these facilities, taking into account their impact on the environment and local culture.

3.5. Stakeholder Involvement

Didimera tourism development is an exciting project and has great potential to improve the local economy, promote cultural and natural heritage, and provide educational and employment opportunities for the local community. Didimera is an area rich in natural beauty, history and culture which has not been fully utilized for tourism purposes. Therefore, tourism development in Didimera is an important step to optimize the potential of the area. Involving stakeholders, be it local government, local communities, the tourism industry, or the general public, is the key to success in creating sustainable and developing tourist destinations. In this research, researchers conducted direct interviews with the village head, Mr. PF. Regarding stakeholders in Didimera tourism development, currently the stakeholders involved in Didimera tourism development are:

- Government (Ministry of Tourism)

According to P.F. in 2021 the Timor Leste Ministry of Tourism will provide funding for the development of tourist villages in all places with tourism potential including Didimera tourism and at that time the regional government of

Vessoru village and the local community submitted a funding proposal to build accommodation, public toilets and rehabilitate the Cave/Gruta. it's in didimera.

- Local government

In developing the Didimera tourist village, the regional government of Vessoru village has the initiative to develop the Didimera tourist area because the place is very strategic and has potential. Therefore, in 2011 the regional government submitted a proposal to the company PT Comico Timor Diak Lda, which at that time was rehabilitating the public highway in Vessoru village, by volunteering to process and repair the Didimera area into a place that all visitors would like.

- Local community

The local community in Vessoru village took the initiative to build the Didimera place as a tourist attraction because the area is very strategic because the weather is friendly, at the foot of the Didimera hill which is close to the beach and on holidays such as New Year, birthdays, everyone always chooses Didimera as their tourist destination.

- Klibur Vessoru Oan (Vessoru Youth Association)

Klibur Vessoru oan (Vessoru Youth Association) is a KVO as an association formed by Vessoru village youth who conducted studies in the capital Dili with the aim of providing various information they obtained from their studies through training, workshops and seminars including Didimera tourism activities. With the activities of the Vessoru Oan Klibur/Vessoru Youth Association in 2010, with contributions from the regional government and local communities, they began to build houses/bungalows and clean up the Didimera area to make it a tourist attraction.

- Student

In 2020, students took the initiative to build a Sapha site for Better Waste Management. With the trash bins built, visitors will be more likely to dispose of their rubbish properly. This helps reduce the amount of rubbish scattered around tourist areas, keeping the environment clean. Thus, the contribution of students from UNTL in building rubbish bins in tourist areas will not only provide practical benefits in environmental management, but will also have a positive impact in terms of education, awareness and sustainable development.

The development of Didimera tourism in Vessoru village is an important step in efforts to utilize the tourism potential of the area. Didimera, with all its natural beauty and cultural heritage, promises the potential to become an attractive tourist destination for local and international tourists. However, tourism development cannot be done alone. It requires involvement and cooperation from various parties who have related interests. In this case, stakeholders play a key role in designing, implementing and managing the Didimera tourism development project (Masitah, 2019).

There are several stakeholders who must be involved in the development of Didimera Tourism in Vessoru Village, Uatolari subdistrict, namely

- Local Government

The village government has the responsibility to provide basic infrastructure, regulate tourism-related regulations, and provide support in the promotion and management of the Didimera tourist destination.

- Local Community

The Vessoru village community is the main stakeholder because they live and interact directly with the tourist environment. Their involvement in decision making, sustainable use of natural resources, and sharing of economic benefits from tourism is essential.

- Company

Companies that have experience in tourism management can build adequate facilities such as homestays, restaurants, shops and other tourism service providers because companies have an interest in increasing income through tourism, but are also responsible for maintaining the quality of services and tourist experiences.

- Non-Governmental Organizations and Non-Governmental Organizations

These organizations can provide support in terms of training, advocacy for environmental and cultural preservation, as well as providing technical assistance in sustainable tourism management.

- Academic

The involvement of academics who have tourism knowledge in Didimera tourism development can provide in-depth insight and knowledge in planning, developing tourism products, and monitoring the impact of tourism on the environment and society. By involving all stakeholders, this will ensure that the development of Didimera tourism in Vessoru village is carried out in a participatory, sustainable and profitable manner for all parties involved. Thus, Didimera tourism can be a valuable resource for local economic development and environmental and cultural preservation in the area.

3.6. Local Community Based Tourism Village Development Strategy

Didimera Vessoru Village, with its natural and cultural riches, has great potential to be developed as an attractive tourist destination. However, to optimize this potential, a directed and sustainable development strategy is needed. The local community-based tourism village development strategy in the area around Didimera must pay attention to the local context, involve active community participation, and pay attention to environmental sustainability. According to the results of the FGD that researchers conducted at the Vessoru village office on 27 December 2023 with discussions to obtain information on strategies for developing local community-based tourism villages in the area around Didimera, Vessoru village focuses on developing the necessary basic infrastructure and tourism, such as expanding the Didimera tourist area to the Caisaheluli location., good roads, parking spaces, sanitation facilities, and clear signage for tourists. Good infrastructure will increase visitor comfort and safety. Based on the results of the Focus Group Discussion conducted by researchers on the Didimera tourism development strategy, it needs to be focused on developing basic infrastructure that supports tourism growth. Some of the main aspects in the FGD results are:

- Strengthening Tourism Infrastructure

Tourist Area Expansion: Expanding the tourist area from Didimera to the Caisaheluli location. This step will expand the range of tourist attractions offered to visitors, increase the attractiveness of the destination, and expand the potential of the local economy. **Increasing Accessibility:** Improving road conditions to tourist locations, including building good and safe roads. Good roads will make access easier for tourists and minimize the risk of accidents.

- Parking Facilities

Build adequate and orderly parking facilities to accommodate the increasing number of tourist vehicles. This will prevent traffic jams and ensure a comfortable visiting experience. **Sanitation Facilities:** Improve sanitation facilities such as public toilets and rubbish bins scattered throughout the tourist area. This will maintain the cleanliness and health of visitors and minimize negative impacts on the environment. **Guidance and Information Signs:** Install clear and informative signs around tourist areas to guide visitors. Complete information about attractions, routes and applicable rules will help visitors explore the destination better.

- Benefits of Infrastructure Development

Increasing Comfort and Security: Good infrastructure will increase the comfort and safety of visitors during their visit to Didimera and its surroundings. **Encouraging Tourism Growth:** With adequate infrastructure, Didimera and Caisaheluli will become more attractive destinations for tourists, which in turn will generate local economic growth through increased visitor numbers and tourism revenues.

- Preserving the Environment

Sustainable infrastructure development must also pay attention to the preservation of the natural environment and local culture. Environmental protection efforts must be integrated into infrastructure planning and development. Increase.

- Local Economy

With the increasing number of visitors, there will be an increase in economic activity around Didimera and Caisaheluli, including in the trade, accommodation, food and drink, and local crafts sectors. Well-planned basic infrastructure development is an important step in optimizing the tourism potential of Didimera and its surroundings. However, it is also important to remember that development must be carried out in a sustainable manner and taking into account the participation and interests of local communities so that the benefits can be felt evenly and sustainably.

Strategy is a way of preparing actions carried out by company managers to achieve the company's mission, goals and objectives (Astuti & Anwar, 2019).

The strategy for developing a local community-based tourism village in the area around Didimera, Vessoru village, is a series of steps aimed at optimizing Didimera's tourism potential by involving active participation and contributions from the local community. This approach emphasizes the importance of paying attention to local context, environmental sustainability and community welfare in developing tourist destinations. It is necessary to develop tourism in Didimera so that it can utilize natural and cultural potential to become an attraction for tourists and tourism development will help utilize this potential more effectively and sustainably, tourism development will open up new opportunities for local communities to generate income from the tourism industry, such as through providing accommodation services, food and beverages, as well as local crafts, with development strategies there will be increased awareness of the importance of preserving cultural heritage and the natural environment. This will encourage efforts to preserve and protect Didimera's cultural and natural riches. Tourism development also requires the construction of basic infrastructure, such as roads, sanitation facilities and parking lots, which will increase accessibility and comfort for visitors. The strategy for developing a local community-based tourism village around Didimera, Vessoru village, refers to the results of the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) which highlights the importance: With the strategy for developing a local community-based tourism village around Didimera, the aim is to ensure that tourism development occurs in a sustainable manner, providing benefits for local communities, and preserving local natural and cultural riches.

4. Conclusion

The conclusion from the various aspects discussed above shows that the development of the Didimera Religious Tourism Village in Vessoru Village, Uatolari District, Viqueque District has great potential to improve the local economy, preserve culture and the environment, and provide a memorable tourism experience for visitors. However, to achieve success in this development, it is important to pay attention to community perception, appropriate tourist design, supporting facilities, and stakeholder involvement.

The perception of the Vessoru Village community towards the development of the Didimera Religious Tourism Village shows the majority of support, although there are still several concerns that need attention, such as environmental sustainability and lack of information about the benefits of tourism development. To increase community support, education, community involvement, transparency, local economic empowerment, and cultural and environmental preservation are needed.

The design of beach-based religious tourism in Didimera must consider combining the natural charm of the beach with a spiritual aura, adequate supporting facilities, consideration of environmental impacts, and effective promotion. In this way, tourists will be able to enjoy a unique and memorable experience while preserving the environment and local culture.

Tourist facilities to support the development of the Didimera tourist destination need to cover various aspects, such as accommodation, tourist information centers, local culinary delights, handicraft centers, recreation facilities, health centers, and waste management facilities and public toilets. By providing quality and varied facilities, Vessoru Village can increase its attractiveness as a sustainable tourist destination.

Stakeholder involvement is also very important in the development of Didimera tourism. Local governments, communities, companies, non-governmental organizations, non-governmental organizations, and academia all have different but important roles in designing, implementing, and managing tourism development projects.

By implementing a holistic and sustainable local community-based tourism village development strategy, Didimera has great potential to become an attractive and sustainable tourist destination. In this way, not only will local economic growth occur, but also environmental and cultural preservation will provide long-term benefits for the entire community.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest to declare.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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